

Quality of Life and Cinematherapy with Dialysis Patients: A Descriptive Study

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ABSTRACT

Chronic Kidney Disease (CKD) is characterized by abnormalities in kidney function or structure lasting at least three months. It can progress to end-stage renal disease (ESRD) when the glomerular filtration rate (GFR) falls below 15 mL/min and albuminuria exceeds 300 mg/24h, necessitating dialysis or transplantation. While dialysis extends survival, it does not cure the disease and is associated with comorbidities and complications that adversely affect the quality of life (QoL). Various factors, including health, work, and emotional well-being influence QoL. This study explored cinematherapy as a complementary intervention during dialysis sessions to enhance QoL in CKD patients. Patients attended cinema sessions during dialysis, and QoL was assessed before and after the sessions using the KDQOL-SFTM1.3 instrument. Results indicated that cinematherapy positively impacted emotional well-being and general health perception. Although more studies are needed, the data suggests cinematherapy may be a useful tool to complement dialysis treatment.

KEYWORDS: Emotions, Complementary therapies, Chronic kidney disease

ARTICLE DETAILS

Published On:
17 October 2025

Available on:
<https://ijmscrs.com/>

I. INTRODUCTION

According to Kidney Disease: Improving Global Outcomes (KDIGO, 2024), Chronic Kidney Disease (CKD) is defined as abnormalities of kidney function or structure, present for at least three months, being classified according to the cause, glomerular filtration rate (GFR) and the presence of albuminuria. Patients with a GFR below 15 mL/min and albuminuria above 300 mg/24h are classified with end-stage renal disease, requiring renal replacement therapy such as dialysis or transplantation. In its most advanced phase, the kidneys cannot maintain the normality of the internal environment and the patient becomes dependent on treatments that replace the function of the kidneys. Dialysis is an invasive treatment that aims to decrease symptoms and increase survival but does not cure

the patient. These patients have comorbidities such as diabetes and hypertension, in addition to complications such as chronic anemia, uremia, calcium metabolism disorders, and sleep disorders (Gonçalves et al., 2015; Webster et al., 2017; Leimig et al., 2018; Zanini et al., 2012).

Because it is a chronic process, it becomes difficult for patients to adapt and adhere to treatment, which reduces their quality of life (QoL) over time. The broad definition of QoL encompasses the degree of satisfaction of human life needs such as work, education, health, leisure, and material elements, along with access to housing, food, and drinking water. Namely, QoL is the individual's perception of their position in life in the context of culture, in conjunction with a value system in which they are inserted, in contrast to their goals, expectations, standards, and concerns (WHO, 2013).

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Therefore, the limitations imposed by dialysis treatment directly impact the individual's life, reducing QoL and well-being, due to the physical effects of the treatment and the social isolation associated with the dialysis routine (Pereira et al, 2012) (Pereira et al, 2017).

Given the above, cinema, generally focused on entertainment, has shown potential in other contexts as a method of motivation. Its influence on people's thinking, attitudes, and lifestyle justifies the use of films in the therapeutic context (Ulus, 2003; Mota, 2016; Herpich, 2023). For this reason, the present study sought to associate cinematherapy as a complementary therapy to minimize the adverse effects of dialysis, in addition to describing the experience with CKD patients on dialysis using cinematherapy as a non-pharmacological intervention, since complementary therapies can help patients, bringing benefits, improvement in QoL and well-being.

II. METHOD

This study was a quantitative, descriptive, and cross-sectional research, conducted between 2021 and 2022, at the UNIRIM dialysis clinic (Portão Unit), in Curitiba-PR. During this period, data collection was performed after the agreement and signing of the informed consent form (ICF) by the patients, according to the control and intervention groups, aiming to obtain a representative sample according to the criteria established for the research. The KDQOL-SFTM1.3 assessment instrument was used and validated for QoL and well-being in CKD patients on dialysis. The version used was translated to Portuguese and approved by the KDQOL Working Group, and the reduced form of the instrument was entitled "Your Health and Well-Being – Kidney Disease and Quality of Life" known as KDQOL-SFTM 1.3 (Duarte et al, 2003). The patients answered the questionnaire, and the intervention group answered after the end of the eight film sessions.

According to the evaluation protocol of the self-report instrument, the closer to 100, the better the score (better QoL). The researchers sought to use accessible language and the average response time to the questionnaire was 20 minutes for each patient. Before using the instrument, the researchers identified the key issues that, in their view, might have the greatest impact on the film sessions, focusing primarily on physical and emotional factors. Patients missing more than two sessions were excluded from the survey.

Patients in the intervention group attended the eight film sessions once a week during the second and third hours of dialysis. The cinematherapy procedure consisted of the screening of films in the room where the patients underwent dialysis. The selection of movies was oriented according to the perception of the authors regarding the motivation and improvement in the well-being of the patients, being in order: "Inside Out" (animation – understanding emotions), "50 First Dates" (comedy – reframing the disease every

day), "13 Going on 30" (comedy – addressing choices), "Luca" (animation – freedom and friendship), "The Pursuit of Happyness" (drama – coping with problems), "The Lion King" (animation – dealing with pain and adapting to loss), "Wonder" (children's drama – adaptations) and "Lion" (drama and biography - concept of home and belonging). The films were selected based on thematic criteria, aiming to address emotional and psychosocial aspects relevant to patients, such as resilience and acceptance.

The data were subjected to normality tests to verify the adequacy of the statistical assumptions. Subsequently, Student's t-test was performed to compare the means between the groups. Statistical significance was considered when $p < 0.05$, with a 95% confidence interval. All analyses were performed using the statistical software GraphPad Prism, version 9.5. The study was submitted to and approved by the Ethics and Research Committee of UFPR, opinion number 5.359.163.

III. RESULTS

Patients were divided into two groups (n=30): intervention group (n=20) and control group (n=10). The age distribution of the participants ranged from 37 to 80 years, with a mean of 60 years, 53% men and 47% women. Most patients self-identified as white (67%), followed by brown (26%) and black (7%). Regarding the type of care, most participants (77%) used the Unified Health System (SUS), while 23% of patients used private care.

Regarding engagement in the intervention group (n=20), those who did not miss any session and watched all the planned films were considered excellent (100%), being great (90%) with one absence (one session) and good (75%) with two absences (two sessions). The result obtained with excellent engagement was 65%, excellent was 25% and good was 10%. In the intervention group, most patients participated in all sessions. Table 1 describes the characteristics of the study samples (Table 1).

Table 1. Characteristics of the study sample

Variables	Control (n=20)	Intervention (n=10)
Gender n (%)		
Female	9 (45)	5 (50)
Male	11 (55)	5 (50)
Age ± SD	61.75 ± 12.27	59.20 ± 13.71
Color n (%)		
White	14 (70)	6 (60)
Brown	5 (25)	3 (30)
Black	1 (5)	1 (10)
Health Insurance Plan n (%)		
Sus	16 (80)	7 (70)
Private	4 (20)	3 (30)

Notes: n: Number; %: Percentage; a: Average; SD: Standard Deviation.

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Statistically significant differences were obtained in several issues addressed, with substantial improvements in the intervention group. Work status showed a significant increase from a mean of 11.11 to 22.37 ($p < 0.0001$) in the intervention group (Table 2).

In terms of the overall health of the sample, a significant improvement was observed, with mean values going from 37.50 to 56.05 ($p = 0.0037$). There was also an improvement in patient satisfaction ($p = 0.005$). Regarding the encouragement of the dialysis team, there was an average of 81.94 in the control group and 95.39 in the intervention group ($p = 0.0038$), showing the superiority of the intervention group.

There was no significant difference between the groups ($p > 0.05$) for most questions, however, some variables showed a significant increase in the mean of the intervention group, such as the weight of the disease, with a mean of 40.28 in the control group compared to 48.34 in the intervention group ($p = 0.1306$). In addition, an improvement in averages was observed in other aspects, such as the effects of kidney disease, emotional well-being, quality of social interaction, energy, sleep, and cognitive function. On the other hand, there was a reduction in the means in certain items, such as physical function, which decreased from 56.17 to 43.57 ($p = 0.0704$), and pain, which went from 64.72 to 59.93 ($p = 0.3264$) (Table 2).

Table 2. Average of the scores obtained by the Control Group and Intervention Group according to KDQOL-SFTM1.3

Issues addressed by KDQOL-SFTM1.3	Control Group Scores m±SD	Intervention Group n Scores m±SD	p*
Patient Satisfaction	62.04 ± 14.91	82.02 ± 22.05	0.0005
Encouragement of dialysis staff	81.94 ± 26.85	95.39 ± 9.38	0.0038
Physical function	56.17 ± 31.19	43.57 ± 28.64	0.0704
Pain	64.72 ± 34.48	59.93 ± 38.08	0.3264
Effects of kidney disease	63.37 ± 15.19	64.89 ± 24.47	0.4052
Weight of kidney disease	40.28 ± 27.97	48.34 ± 27.87	0.1306
General Health	37.50 ± 17.93	56.05 ± 25.42	0.0037
Emotional well-being	57.78 ± 27.82	58.11 ± 26.10	0.4830
Quality of social interaction	76.67 ± 18.89	82.11 ± 17.13	0.1439
Energy/fatigue	46.39 ± 27.54	50.79 ± 25.27	0.2784
Sleep	59.86 ± 26.85	68.36 ± 24.52	0.1227
Cognitive function	71.11 ± 23.87	81.23 ± 21.69	0.0602
Working status	11.11 ± 21.39	22.37 ± 30.08	<0.0001

Notes: m: Mean; SD: Standard deviation. *p shows a significant difference when < 0.05 .

When analyzing the overall means of the two groups (control and intervention), a significant difference was observed ($p = 0.0119$), indicating that the study obtained a positive result in improving the participants' quality of life after the action (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Comparison between means of the control and intervention groups

Key: KDQOL-SFTM1.3 score. $p < 0.05$ shows a significant difference between the control vs. intervention groups.

IV. DISCUSSION

CKD is a condition characterized by progressive and irreversible loss of renal function over time. It is diagnosed when the glomerular filtration rate (GFR) is less than 60 mL/min/1.73 m² or when renal lesions, such as albuminuria, hematuria, or structural changes, are present for at least three months (KDIGO, 2024). In these conditions, dialysis is indicated as an essential therapy in the treatment of advanced CKD, replacing the function of the kidneys by filtering and removing waste and liquids from the blood by a semi-permeable extracorporeal membrane, helping to maintain the electrolyte balance and quality of life of patients (Fleming, 2011). Dialysis, although vital for CKD patients, may be associated with complications such as infections, hypotension, electrolyte imbalances, and fatigue, impacting patients' quality of life and professional performance. In addition, it leads to changes in the perception of one's own health, negatively impacting energy and vitality levels, which can lead to reduced social interactions and cause problems related to mental health (Duarte et al, 2003; Jesus et al., 2019). Despite this, the QoL of these patients, for a long time, was evaluated exclusively in terms of survival and signs of the presence of the disease, without considering psychosocial issues (Taylor et al, 1990).

Because it is a broad, dynamic, and subjective concept, one of the great challenges in the study of QoL is to develop ways for comparison and measurement. Considering the wider definition of QoL, which considers the individual's

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perception of their values and position in life (Brasil, 2023), more recently, QoL assessment instruments have included data on physical, psychological, and social condition and functioning, in addition to the impact of disease symptoms and treatment. A study demonstrated that the QoL of dialysis patients was lower than that of the normative group, both in the physical and psychological domains, and that there are variables that influence the perception of QoL, so they should be considered in the clinical evaluation (Jesus et al., 2019). Another prospective cohort study with patients with CKD showed that the presence of depression was a high-risk factor for hospitalization and progression of kidney disease (Hedayati et al., 2010).

The present study described the issues addressed by the KDQOL-SFTM1.3 in the context of activities conducted in a specialized dialysis clinic, evaluating cinematherapy as a complementary intervention to treatment to reduce the negative impact of dialysis on patients with CKD. Initially, the concern was with patient engagement, in this regard, the descriptive analysis showed that most showed excellent engagement, suggesting that cinema sessions can be a motivator, improving patient adherence to treatment. Another point that corroborates this perception is that the patients in the control group, who were not part of the film sessions, asked the researchers to also participate in the intervention group.

Movie scenes can unfold unconscious mental contents and induce emotional responses. While watching a movie, we realize this in a particular way. Films help to shape the viewer's life, transforming it into "art", that is, into something that he can absorb, reflect, and store. Cinema shapes the reality that people need to live and know about what they live (Ullus, 2003; Hauke, 2009; Herpich, 2023). Based on this, the films chosen and used in the research were considered relevant to the perception of the researchers, as highlighted in the methodology of the work. The researchers considered some important criteria when choosing the films, such as the ability to generate a sense of well-being or connection with a character or motivation, to improve positive emotions, and on the other hand, that the films did not trigger some unwanted triggers in patients.

According to our data, scores close to 100 were observed regarding patient satisfaction and encouragement of the dialysis team, each with a difference greater than 10 points between the control and intervention groups. It is worth noting that concerning team encouragement, there was already a high score in the group without intervention. The scores related to the clinical part of the patient, such as physical function and pain, do not suggest improvement after the film sessions.

The presence of clinical complications resulting from loss of renal function are known, such as chronic anemia, calcium metabolism disorders, seizures, headache, nausea, vomiting, malaise, muscle cramps, air embolism, phlebitis, pruritus, tiredness, inability to have children and sleep

disorders (Hill et al., 2016; Jesus et al., 2018; Lira et al., 2015; Terra et al., 2010), however, to evaluate these issues, clinical data and laboratory markers of patients would have to be analyzed. As is known, the instrument applied in this article referred only to the patient's perception of their physical function. A situation like that of physical function and pain was observed with the effect of kidney disease and weight of kidney disease, in which there was an increase in the score in the intervention group, but which did not exceed 10 points.

Such findings may suggest that there was no difference between the groups, however, it is understood that in the complexity of kidney disease and its invasive treatment, even without impact on the reduction of clinical complications, the film sessions alleviated, even momentarily, the difficulties; as well as it can be observed concerning general health, emotional well-being, quality of social interaction and energy/fatigue, which presented higher scores in the intervention group, being important to highlight that there was a difference greater than 10 points suggesting an improvement in the patient's perception in the case of their "general health". Namely, in the questions involving emotional status, there was a significant improvement in the intervention group.

Many patients with CKD report some complaints about sleep disorders and excessive daytime sleepiness, being the third most frequent complaint. The relationship between sleep quality and renal health is interconnected and is a crucial factor for the balance of the renal system. During sleep, hormonal regulation processes essential for renal health occur (Hill et al., 2016; Jesus et al., 2018; Lira et al., 2015; Terra et al., 2010). Poor sleep quality such as insomnia, apnea, and restless legs syndrome leads to increased stress with physical and mental consequences for the patient (Fonseca et al., 2014). In the present study, a significant improvement of more than 10 points was observed in the intervention group about sleep. However, it is considered early to state that this fact can be associated only with the use of films, or if any other factor should be associated. The same occurred with cognitive function, which also improved the perception of patients in the intervention group. These findings are promising but should be considered that patients were faced with a novelty and perhaps motivated by it.

The work status also showed an improvement of more than 10 points in the intervention group, which may suggest that film sessions have motivated patients to overcome challenges, but it would also be rash to infer this result only from the use of films. This fact could be explained by the coincidence of the control group having more unemployed patients. In any case, the low score in this regard is noteworthy, both in the control group and in the intervention group, which leads us to believe in the great difficulty of being able to work simultaneously with dialysis treatment. Another important information that the study showed was

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the low scores obtained in general, with several scores around 50 and even below that, such as physical function and weight of kidney disease, in addition to the work status discussed above. Such findings may be a consequence of the difficulties and limitations imposed by the disease, its complications, and dialysis treatment.

Some authors suggest that the application of the questionnaire depends on the objective to be achieved, if the objective is to routinely monitor a relatively stable patient, it can be used 2 to 4 times a year if the patient is starting dialysis treatment or has presented changes in medication or dialysis prescription, more frequent evaluations should be performed (Duarte et al. 2003). These authors also reflect that the application of the questionnaire during the dialysis procedure may affect the assessment of QoL, due to psychological influences due to the momentary relationship with the dialysis machine, and that it would be desirable for the assessment not to be carried out during the dialysis session (Duarte et al, 2003). However, in our work, the objective was precisely to reduce the negative impact of dialysis through film sessions, and, therefore, the questionnaires were applied during this period.

Among the limitations found by the researchers were the infrastructure for the cinema sessions during the dialysis treatment, from the installation of the projectors, issues such as the ambient sound for an adequate sense of "cinema", associated with the noise of the dialyzing machines and the interruption by the multidisciplinary team, which had priority in the care given to patients. One observation of the authors was that those patients who chose not to participate in the cinema sessions stayed practically all the time, that is, during the four hours of dialysis, using their cell phones. Finally, another important situation that needs to be reported is the presence of patients with vision or hearing difficulties who chose to participate, in these cases, the researchers sought to bring them closer to the movie screen, to improve visibility and hearing.

Within this context and despite the difficulties encountered, the experience was enriching in the sense of envisioning ways to reduce the negative impact of an invasive treatment such as dialysis and seeking to improve the QoL and well-being of these patients.

CONCLUSIONS

In the current scenario of growth in the number of dialysis patients who, in turn, live increasingly, it is imperative to be concerned with QoL. There is still a greater concentration of efforts on clinical parameters directly related to kidney disease, intending to increase patient survival, although sometimes to the detriment of QoL. The main findings highlight the benefits observed in the intervention group, particularly concerning the patients' emotional well-being. In this regard, it is important to differentiate the psychological approach, which emphasizes the individual's reactions to their experiences, from medical

theories, which focus on the healing and survival of individuals.

Finally, it is suggested that the findings described, although promising concerning the use of cinematherapy, need further studies with a larger number of patients, and that the present study can be directed to other groups of patients with chronic non-communicable diseases, with invasive and prolonged treatments.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

We thank the team of the specialized dialysis clinic (UNIRIM – Portão Unit) and particularly the nephrologist Dr. Michelle Oliveira Mota, for allowing the development of the project during the dialysis sessions

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